
Cliental Network of Biala Podlaska 1702-1709: An Attempt at Qualitative Analysis of Patronage Networking

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Abstract

Patronage in Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth has been often portrayed as a dominant mechanism of social advancement in Early Modern period. It has been noted, however, that horizontal relationships between people of similar status were often as important in securing career and improving or securing social standing (Starchenko 2018). Thus, relationships between members of a cliental network need to be studied as well, since they mark a distinct area of social activity in which people of varied, but nonetheless relatively subservient status intermingled.

The question of supportive networks is especially important when discussing periods such as the Great Northern War (1700-1721), which brought widespread destruction and political strife to the Commonwealth, causing a deep societal and economical crisis. The same wartime difficulties, that could've made patron's aid indispensable, caused him to be often absent, thus replacing personal contact with (unreliable) written communication. Such an environment would seem a favourable condition for forming horizontal networks, operating nonetheless under protection of a certain patron.

My research is focused on the network focused around Karol Stanislaw Radziwill, Grand Chancellor of Lithuania, at the beginning of 18th century (1700 to 1719). The base of my source material is correspondence exchanged primarily between Radziwill and his clients, located in the Radziwill family archive (part of AGAD in Warsaw). Letter networks have been already studied (eg. Ahnert and Ahnert, 2015); however, even such an unusually well-preserved magnate's archive follows the framework of a specific egocentric network. Actual relationships must be revealed through what clients reported about each other to a shared patron. Thus, the network transgresses the framework of correspondents whose letters are preserved.

I'm presenting an example of local network, based around the Radziwill's estates in Brest voievodship and centered in Biala Podlaska. Having started the query from persons with a common denominator of locality, I'm moving onto relations internal and external, both spatially and in terms of patronage structures. Those include relations based on various aspects of patronage and clientelism (eg. estate management, local politics, communication), as well as clients' relations which are not influenced (at least markedly) by patronage. Tasks assigned to clients are of varied importance; for example, a person with good familial connections could be chosen to deal with local dietine, which was a sign of large trust conferred by patron (Zielińska 1971). Through differentiating certain relations, specified clusters might

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emerge within the network. By looking at how those influence openness and various types of centrality, I'm seeking to understand how network could develop vertical hierarchy, and how a member of the network could receive aid from within the network itself.

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